

Peer Learning in Diverse Undergraduate Population in Networking and Distributed Computing Research

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Abstract

Research has shown peer learning to provide a more welcoming environment to diverse student populations. Computer Science courses, such as Computer Networks, Distributed Computing, and Computer and Network Security, require multiple computers to test the developments beyond simulations, emulations, or virtual execution environments such as virtual machines. While each student is usually equipped with a personal computer, they must rely on computer labs to access research clusters for physically distributed executions. Such reliance poses additional hurdles. For example, students lack permission to install and run software on lab computers, and university security policies prevent students from running specific tasks, such as mimicking a network attack between two computer nodes in the university network for educational purposes. Students may use web-based computational resources such as Cloud Computing as an alternative. However, that incurs ongoing costs, often limited by the instructor's funding availability. This paper presents our approach to peer learning as student-driven group research projects in undergraduate classes. The instructor teaches these subjects as hybrid courses, with students joining in person or virtually. The classes consist of diverse student populations. This paper looks into our approach to incrementally defining student-driven networking and distributed computing research and their contribution to peer learning. In one instance, students conducted networking and distributed computing research on their personal computers, configured to communicate in a private network. They found such executions easier and more effective than installing and configuring several custom software in the lab computers, as those would require escalation for permission requests. We further present our incremental optimization process for these undergraduate research projects for an effective active learning environment.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Peer Learning; Project-Based Learning (PBL).

1 Introduction

Computer Science (CS) modules such as Distributed Computing and Computer Networks typically require the presence of a compute cluster for the projects to be implemented in a physical infrastructure. While many universities are equipped with such infrastructure, they limit the students' access to them as not all universities and schools have sufficient resources, especially when a group of students need access to those simultaneously. Some reserved labs also require physical presence to use their resources, which will challenge remote learners by requiring them to commute to their campus. Security is another concern that drives universities to limit students from configuring network applications that can communicate between computers. As an alternative strategy, researchers and learners use simulations (Breslau et al., 2000), emulations (Jurgelionis et al., 2011), and virtualized execution environments (Ammons et al., 2007) such as virtual machines (VMs). While they provide an alternative learning environment, they do not sufficiently provide the same realistic experience and exposure to the students as using a physical cluster developed with actual computers in a distributed manner.

Another commonly used approach is relying on cloud computing. However, that comes with additional limitations. First, while specific research labs are awarded with cloud credits from major cloud providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) (Cloud, 2011), Microsoft Azure (Wilder, 2012), and Google Cloud Platform (GCP) (Bisong & Bisong, 2019), they are not widely available to many non-R1/R2 universities in the US or many smaller universities globally. Furthermore, undergraduate courses such as Computer Networks cannot readily be

taught in cloud environments as teaching cloud access and security are often outside the scope of these courses, given the limited time in the semester. Therefore, peer learning that utilizes students' devices works better in courses that require resources not readily available in undergraduate-focused universities. The goal of peer learning in collaborative courses such as Distributed Computing and Computer Networks and their associated research is to facilitate a student-driven research agenda without getting limited by the lack of resources in the research clusters by augmenting the computational resources in the labs with student's personal computers, by providing a seamless execution environment for students, between the research clusters in the labs and clusters that could be formed with the personal computers of student groups.

However, peer learning comes with further challenges in diverse environments. University of Alaska Anchorage (UAA) has a Carnegie Classification of "Master's Colleges & Universities: Larger Programs" (Shulman, 2001) and is an Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander Serving Institution (Nguyen et al., 2018). Anchorage is often cited as the most diverse city in the US. The top-3 most diverse schools in the US are all in the Anchorage School District (Farrell, 2018). With a (year 2023) population of 10,845 students with 5.43% American Indian/Native American, 7.26% Asian, 2.77% Black, 8.41% Hispanic/Latino, and 2.61% Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander, UAA is often considered a minority-serving institution. In addition to its main campus in Anchorage, UAA has community colleges that serve Alaskan Native communities, who often transfer to complete their degrees at the Anchorage campus. A large fraction of UAA undergraduates are non-traditional students: Some are the first in their families to attend university. Some started university after the age of 25. Some have family responsibilities. Some are also full-time employees and/or the primary caretaker of a dependent in their house. For many such students, employment is necessary to finance their education. Many students do not follow the same academic path. Subsequently, a senior student often still can have several unfamiliar classmates. Consequently, UAA is blessed with a diverse student population.

This paper proposes peer learning in the context of undergraduate research group projects in networking and distributed computing modules. These hands-on projects leverage the undergraduates' computational resources to compose clusters for their research. The approach is tasked with understanding the human challenges associated with undergraduate group research projects in a diverse student population, especially with increased freedom to create and use their own research clusters through a well-defined framework provided by the instructor. Students are given the resources to develop their research clusters on their personal devices and work synergistically for individual and group success. Thus, we aim to promote active learning and peer learning among the students with minimal friction. Our early observations show that commuter students welcome this approach, as they could form groups with students who live nearby rather than commuting to the campus for their project implementation and group meetings. This freedom is crucial for a university that serves a large state such as Alaska, where classes are hybrid (students can join the class in person or remotely through Zoom). Catering to the two categories of students (those who primarily join in-person vs. those who mostly join remotely) and ensuring the teams consist of the same category of students (and incorporating location-based preferences and other parameters in group formations) are exciting research problems.

2 Motivation

Volunteer computing (Cunsolo et al., 2009) has allowed personal computational resources to be shared to execute larger complex computational tasks in a decentralized manner (Atre et al., 2021). However, volunteer computing typically focuses on sharing computational or network resources for a popular processing or network measurement task. Peer-to-peer (Milojicic et al., 2002) computation frameworks have helped create overlay networks and run distinct applications on top of them. However, peer-to-peer applications that can run on overlay networks are bound by the underlying physical network and its middlebox functions, such as

firewalls. The overlay networks also cannot run many distributed systems as decentralized applications are a class of their own. Not all network applications can execute in such a peer-to-peer environment. This proposed project's technological complexity is relatively trivial. It merely connects the students' personal computers through switches and ethernet cables while ensuring security best practices are followed. The major contribution from this project comes from the academic challenges and interpersonal skills associated with carrying out such projects successfully. Facilitating a peer learning environment with established groups comes with challenges, including setting up student expectations, providing them access to the technical framework and network equipment (switches) as needed, and empowering them to quickly configure a secure private network for their projects. Since this will be a repeating task across modules, ensuring that the identified solution can be reproducible and optimizing it with each iteration are essential. Our approach, a paradigm shift in team formation and project definition, increases the computational capacity of the undergraduate student population by enabling them to leverage their personal computers to form research clusters quickly, using state-of-the-art networking developments.

In parallel to the students' research works on the topics, we also learn how student teams can function effectively towards undergraduate research, utilizing their shared computational resources and making their private networks across their devices. Our framework follows student-centric approaches to innovating pedagogy for project-based learning (Kokotsaki et al., 2016) in courses that benefit the most from such collaborative activities. While group projects are common in computer science and other STEM education, their efficiency in achieving learning outcomes with better student satisfaction in diverse education settings remains an important research topic. As a diverse university, UAA makes an excellent site for our associated research on student satisfaction and success in such project-based learning approaches. These group projects are formulated with students' direct inputs and directions with a larger degree of freedom for the student groups, including their implementation (in the form of software programming, deployment, and evaluation/benchmarking), demonstration (presentation, posters, or software executions), dissemination (code documentation, research papers, and conference talks), and archival (open-source in a GitHub repository). The project ideas are defined broadly for the students' interpretation and expansion rather than molding them into an inflexible project. However, to ensure direction and progress, continuous consultation for feedback is made compulsory with a well-defined framework with which students work. Such meetings are facilitated synchronously (face-to-face or virtually) and asynchronously via Email and Discord text communications.

While our project-based learning is carried out for the undergraduates enrolled in one department for the identified courses, some findings may be extended to other STEM educational settings, such as community colleges and high schools. Data collection regarding student satisfaction and demographics will involve human subjects. Therefore, we are preparing for the necessary Institutional Resource Board (IRB) approvals for more comprehensive surveys/questionnaires and a quantitative framework to measure student motivation, satisfaction, and success, supported by clearly stated consent forms. This quantitative framework will be developed parallel to the technical framework facilitating peer learning research groups. As such, our research combines innovations in networks and distributed systems and STEM education.

We identify Computer Networks, Distributed Computing, and related courses as the target for this project as these directly apply to the requirement of having multiple computers operating in a networked cluster. However, the lessons from this project can be generalized into other educational settings in similar 4-year public universities. By combining the pedagogical innovations in peer learning, project-based learning, group projects, and flipped learning (Yarbro et al., 2014) into the undergraduate computer science curriculum, specifically innovations in network and distributed computing architectures. We build a standard network framework that students can replicate using their personal laptops and utility network hardware to work on

their group projects as a team in their own research clusters. While there is no scientific novelty in such network configurations, formalizing them into pedagogy to actively promote teams to be more interdependent on team members is an exciting innovation in computer science education.

3 Methods

As the first step, we prototyped a reusable network framework for the students to replicate. We discuss the security considerations and best practices needed for students to securely connect their computers to form clusters from the computer lab or homes when network switches and cables are available. We standardize this step so that we can repeat this across courses without additional repeated effort. Students work in teams from their preferred locations. This will benefit many students as UAA is a commuter campus, and many students tend to work outside the campus and often remotely on their group projects. Physical proximity to each other can be a defining factor in the success of the groups, which is considered when the groups are formed. Open-source execution frameworks are proposed with the networking hardware for communication across the student computers.

Figure 1 shows the private network formations of the teams, each team with four members by default (and five members when needed) connecting their devices via a network switch. Excess unused network hardware in the labs, such as NETGEAR 5-Port Gigabit Ethernet Unmanaged Switches (GS305) and RJ45 cables, allow students to connect their computers into clusters without configuring additional software. These switches cost less than 20 USD and are low-cost hardware compared to computers and enterprise software. Therefore, they can be easy to obtain and scale the teams. On top of that networked environment, students then deploy and execute their programs as well as open-source distributed execution environments such as Infinispan (Marchioni, 2012), Hazelcast (Johns, 2015), and GridGain (Samovsky & Kacur, 2012) In-Memory Data Grids (IMDG) (Guroob & Manjaiah, 2017) environments to allow running their software in a distributed manner.

Figure 1. Private network clusters of the teams

The project and group formation consider the potential for one or at most two students from a team to drop out during the period of the course and group project. Such a dropout or withdrawal of students is indeed a potential across many classes. However, by carefully designing the problem, the impact of such a scaling down could be prevented. Computer and network security is critical, especially regarding data privacy, even in a private network. The students are trained in security and ethics to protect themselves and their teammates in such network deployments.

The instructor posts a list of potential project ideas (a title and a brief description/abstract) for each course early in the semester. Then, each student provides an ordered subset of their preferred topics from the list. Then, the instructor forms teams of students who show interest in working on the same topic, assigning the project ideas to the students who choose those with the highest preference as much as possible. There will be a wide range of project ideas for any student to choose from.

Once the teams are formed and the project ideas are assigned, the students follow a well-defined timeline, independently as teams, on their assigned topics. For the success of the projects, teams are formed considering their research interest (as indicated by their preferences on project ideas) and availability (students may be assigned to their second or third preference project if their higher preference projects have a higher demand). Demographics are considered in team formation so that students belonging to minorities in coding are not left alone in a team without a peer from a minority community. This ensures better participation from all the students. Teams are made diversely while considering such practical aspects. The teams are formed under the broadly defined project idea, in which the teams work together, with the instructor's input, to develop a more detailed problem statement and implementation from the instructor-provided project abstract. This team formation will be incrementally enhanced over the years as the instructor teaches the courses annually, considering student feedback and the overall quality of their research outcomes.

These projects are designed to enhance the students' higher-order skills defined in Bloom's Taxonomy. The learning outcomes are specified to improve students' creativity beyond what is achieved in a lecture-centric class or a classic group project where students work on a well-defined task provided by the instructor. The rubrics define the learning outcomes to ensure a thorough understanding of the problem. Sample learning outcomes from one of the group research projects from the class (on Computer and Network Security) are as in Listing 1.

This activity corresponds to the below student learning outcomes:

- 1. Analyze potential risks in designing and implementing operating systems, databases, software, cloud, and networks.*
- 2. Create innovative solution architectures adhering to the best practices of confidentiality, integrity, and availability, leveraging recent advancements in network security.*
- 3. Evaluate threats and vulnerabilities in an organization, including physical and infrastructure security, human resources security, software security, network security, and data privacy.*

Listing 1. Learning outcomes from a group project.

These outcomes specifically target Create, Evaluate, and Analyze as their learning goals, instead of the projects where the students are tasked with Apply, Understand, and Remember skills. In addition, personal and professional capabilities (or transversal competencies), such as "organize group work and task distribution" and "document the evolution of the project work," are included as secondary learning outcomes. Each team will have a leader elected by the team and options to fire an idling teammate or quit when every other teammate does not contribute. The students who quit and those who are fired have to meet with the instructor to find alternative avenues to complete the assignment and receive a grade for the project. Students also have the option to switch teams in the early phases of the project with a valid reason. However, switching teams is discouraged since such changes contradict the instructor's original reasoning when forming the teams.

The project ideas posted for the students to choose from have sufficient details to ignite interest from the students (as by that time, they have a basic understanding of the topic but have yet to progress much into the course). Students are encouraged to meet with the instructor to clarify the topics before choosing one. Students work on expanding the idea into a fully-fledged project requirement to implement the solution for the task, following a flipped learning approach since most of the knowledge relevant to the topics is taught later in the course, whereas students start on the project early in the semester. Since these tasks are distinct across the projects, the student presentations by the end of the semester will be educational, and the instructor and other students will be able to learn from the students who present their work. Two sample project ideas (among the 14 listed for the Fall 2023 semester of the Computer Networks course) are shown in Listing 2.

The rubrics also include points to be given by the teammates and students from other teams as they evaluate the projects' outcomes based on a demo. In a sample group project of 10 points, the instructor awards 6 points, whereas students award the other 4 points. Each student will be asked to evaluate their peers' contributions on a 3-point scale: Incomplete (0 / Student did not make any contribution to this aspect of the project), Satisfactory (1 / Student made a considerable contribution to this aspect), and Excellent (2 / Student made an excellent contribution to this aspect).

The students are given a form to evaluate their peers close to the deadline with their scores to other students from their teams on their contribution to overall team success. The final score under this component will be a geometric mean of all the scores received by the student. Peers are expected to justify their score. That means the students cannot just give a score (2, 1, or 0). Instead, they should also explain why they think their peer deserves this point – and no less and no more. For instance, one receiving a “0” score must have actively hindered the progress of the teamwork, at least for the student evaluating this teammate. This approach ensures a voice for each student. If a single student in the team is cornered and feels unsupported by their peers, they could make 0 points with justification, thus making the unsupportive peer's geometric mean get 0. We hypothesize that such a construct is expected to motivate fair contributions from students, prevent idle partners, and encourage collaboration with teammates.

Similarly, during the final day of the projects, all the students from other groups evaluate the demos on the same Incomplete (0), Satisfactory (1), and Excellent (2) scale. The final score under this component will be an arithmetic mean of all the scores received by the student. We anticipate that while the teammates will score each member differently, other students are more likely to grade all team members equally. However, the instructor will carefully and individually grade each member's contribution to ensure no freeloaders in the team. Each team's work is considered for a research publication, with corrections and enhancements from the instructor. The students will be able to voice their opinions of the group projects, peer learning activities, and overall learning experience through their faculty evaluation and questionnaires at the end of each semester, which will facilitate the annual review of the instructor. These additional measures ensure a continuous improvement to the team formation. Interested students may continue to work on their research papers with the instructor beyond their course timeline to refine their work for publication.

We will evaluate the overall success of our proposed approach through the semester-end anonymous student survey outcomes on faculty evaluation and student success. We will compare the results across the modules and prior years before the proposed system and during the iterations across semesters to ensure continuous progress and improvements.

I) Net Neutrality Debate and Content-Aware Networking

The net neutrality regulations mandate that Internet Service Providers (ISPs) cannot discriminate on connectivity based on the nature of the application. Net neutrality ensures fair access to all the legal content to the end users, preventing the ISPs from blocking or throttling websites or prioritizing content that is paid a premium for. Such fair access is a crucial component in maintaining equal access to the websites. However, enterprises always try to push these regulations for their profits. Zero-rating offers are an example. Specific applications are bundled and offered for free or at a better-performing data rate. Some examples of offers are from MEO.pt in Portugal in 2017 and Vodafone in New Zealand. These preferential offerings may negatively impact other Internet data traffic, including critical web applications such as telehealth visits and tele-education. On the other hand, content-aware networking research focuses on leveraging the knowledge of the content to provide better access to critical content. For instance, what if these Internet "fast lanes" are offered for telehealth instead? However, their applicability in routing and scheduling data based on content and how they will violate net neutrality are questioned. This project will look into content-aware networking and how they can operate without compromising the net neutrality principles (or can they not?) An emulated application can be a plus.

N) Federated network architectures

This project looks into network communication mechanisms across multiple network domains. While classic network switches have both a data plane and a control plane in each of them, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) unifies them to have logically centralized control. However, such unified control and management is feasible only when a single entity (such as a company or university) owns and manages the entire network.

When multiple organizations want to coordinate their networks, the network communication cannot resemble such unified access and control, as centralized control in such environments will not make sense. Protected access to the networks, while sharing minimal control across the domains, is essential in such scenarios.

That is when federated networks come into play. These networks can span multiple organizations or multiple clouds. They can also function with SDN, providing a federated orchestration of controllers belonging to various network domains. Students understand and learn how network protocols scale beyond the data center level in this project. We have learned about data centers, enterprise networks, and the Internet. Here, we focus on somewhere in between - a network of networks that is not the Internet. But instead, a federated network. This group will also evaluate the current federated network architectures and the future trends.

Listing 2. Two illustrative project ideas in Computer Networks from Fall 2023.

4 Discussion

Our project-based learning approach aims to build capacity in STEM education, specifically undergraduate computer science, by augmenting the computational capacities of the class/lab with students' devices working as a cluster for group projects. We envision fostering efficient, reusable mechanisms to formulate robust and self-sustaining student groups. We identified specific modules (Computer Networks, Computer and Network Security, and Distributed Systems) as the applications for this project, as these modules typically require more than one computational node for their physical implementation. However, the developed framework can be used for other computer science and engineering modules and other STEM disciplines in general. We aim to obtain feedback and adoption from other faculty for other CS modules to test the approach's applicability in a broader sense.

Several factors contribute to challenges in students' academic success. Supportive peer learning environments have been shown to reduce those barriers to academic excellence in marginalized communities (Tai et al.,

2017). Therefore, we anticipate positive outcomes from fostering peer learning exercises in the class rather than having only the lecturer-centric traditional lectures, with an increased sense of belonging and peer mentoring across the student groups (Won et al., 2018). An inclusive classroom and peer learning may foster creative freedom among the students by providing a non-judgmental environment (Ballard et al., 2008). First-generation undergraduates have more barriers to entry into STEM research than those from academic families (Stebbleton & Soria, 2013). This need for support emanates from the students being first in their families and homes to enter higher education and who face challenges in overcoming psychological issues caused by their educational programs, many times involving linguistic, disability, economic need, and health issues.

This project is a pilot for undergraduate CS classes with a large, diverse student population, requiring access to extensive distributed computational resources with limited availability. The instructor commits to offering a student-centric education through a place-based learning approach, with greater importance and respect to projects that contribute to the land and the local communities. The continuous feedback from the students throughout the courses and the semester-end surveys will allow us to develop a self-improving, reproducible model that can facilitate similar delivery across other CS classes, especially those modules that can benefit from hands-on programming and software development challenges, with a greater need for communication and collaboration across multiple computers forming a cluster for a realistic physical execution. We will evaluate how an inclusive classroom will benefit the students through our project-based learning approach with greater freedom in team performance. Combined with active learning approaches such as flipped learning, we anticipate the projects will form a crucial pillar in their education journey in the associated courses.

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